

PROCEEDING

Black hole masses from emission-line widths

Elena Dalla Bontà^{1,2}

¹Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “G. Galilei”, Università di Padova, Padova, Italy

²INAF—Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Padova, Italy

Correspondence

Elena Dalla Bontà, Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “G. Galilei”, Università di Padova

Vicolo dell’ Osservatorio 3, I-35122 Padova, Italy.

Email: elena.dallabonta@unipd.it

Abstract

Reverberation mapping and scaling relationships based on reverberation results provide the underpinning of all estimates of quasar black hole masses. When applying these scaling relationships, there are potential pitfalls that are widely unappreciated and can result in biases that can, in turn, lead to systematic errors in the black hole mass function and therefore conclusions about the evolution of black holes over time. Here we discuss specifically the suitability of various line-width measures for estimating black hole masses.

KEYWORDS

reverberation mapping, black hole masses, emission-line widths

1 | INTRODUCTION

Reverberation mapping (RM) of broad emission lines (Blandford & McKee 1982; Peterson 1993) is by far the most common direct method of measuring the masses of black holes (BHs) in active galactic nuclei (Peterson 2014). This technique makes use of the intrinsic variability of the central continuum source and the light travel-time delay of the emission-line response to these variations to determine the size R of the broad-line region (BLR). With high-quality velocity-resolved reverberation measurements, the BH mass can be determined independent of any other measurements (Grier et al. 2013b, 2017a; Pancoast et al. 2011, 2014). More commonly, however, only an average response time, or lag, τ is measured from reverberation data. In such cases, the BH mass is computed from

$$M_{\text{BH}} = f \left(\frac{\Delta V^2 R}{G} \right), \quad (1)$$

where ΔV is the emission-line width, $R = c\tau$ is the size of the BLR from the reverberation lag, and G is the gravitational constant. The quantity in parentheses is

often referred to as the virial product; it incorporates the two observables in RM, the line width and time delay, and is in units of mass. The scaling factor f is a dimensionless quantity of order unity that depends on the geometry, kinematics, and inclination of the AGN, and so is different for each AGN: without determining the velocity-dependent reverberation response of the emission line, it is not possible to determine f uniquely for a given AGN. However, a mean value $\langle f \rangle$ can be determined for an ensemble of AGNs if another mass-indicator is available. In practice, $\langle f \rangle$ has been determined by assuming that the $M - \sigma_*$ relationship is the same in AGNs and quiescent galaxies (Batiste et al. 2017; Grier et al. 2013a; Onken et al. 2004; Woo et al. 2015). Justification for use of Equation (1) is provided by the well-documented anticorrelation between emission-line lags and line widths in the cases where multiple lines have been measured in the same source (Bentz et al. 2010; Kollatschny 2003; Onken & Peterson 2002; Peterson & Wandel 1999, 2000).

A remarkable result of RM is the correlation between the size of the BLR as measured by reverberation with the

This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2021 The Authors. *Astronomische Nachrichten* published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

luminosity L of the AGN. This “radius–luminosity relationship” (Bentz et al. 2006, 2009, 2013; Kaspi et al. 2000, 2005) is roughly of the form $R \propto L^{1/2}$. This means that one can estimate the AGN BH mass from a single spectrum—the BLR radius can be inferred from the AGN luminosity,¹ the line width can be measured, and the mass is then inferred from Equation (1), bypassing the resource-intensive requirements of RM (Corbett et al. 2003; Fine et al. 2008; Kollmeier et al. 2006; McLure & Jarvis 2002; Shen et al. 2008a, 2008b; Vestergaard 2002, 2004; Vestergaard et al. 2008; Vestergaard & Peterson 2006; Wandel et al. 1999). There are, however, a number of subtleties that must be recognized:

1. Recent studies have shown that the radius–luminosity relationship requires a third parameter, which seems to be Eddington ratio (Dalla Bontà et al. 2020; Du et al. 2016, 2018; Du & Wang 2019; Fonseca Alvarez et al. 2020; Grier et al. 2017b; Martínez-Aldama et al. 2019). This does not obviate the use of radius–luminosity relationship, but it does add another level of complexity to computing masses.
2. What parameter should be used to characterize the line width? The two most commonly used parameters are full-width at half maximum (FWHM) and line dispersion, i.e., the square root of the second moment of the line,

$$\sigma_{\text{line}} = \left[\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} v^2 P(v) dv}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(v) dv} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (2)$$

where $P(v)$ is the emission-line profile as a function of line-of-sight (Doppler) velocity v . The ratio of FWHM/ σ_{line} varies with line width, so these two parameters cannot be used interchangeably. Which measure better characterizes BH masses? Are there other measures that should be considered?

Another important issue is that the variable part of an emission line may have a different profile and width than what is seen in an individual or mean spectrum. In RM analysis, it is common to construct a mean spectrum from the N spectra obtained during the monitoring period,

$$\bar{F}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N F_i(\lambda), \quad (3)$$

where $F_i(\lambda)$ is the flux in the i th spectrum of the time series at wavelength λ . It is also possible to construct a root-mean-square residual spectrum (hereafter simply

“rms spectrum”), which is defined as

$$\sigma_{\text{rms}}(\lambda) = \left\{ \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_1^N [F_i(\lambda) - \bar{F}(\lambda)]^2 \right\}^{1/2}. \quad (4)$$

The rms spectrum effectively isolates the variable part of the spectrum and, in particular, the emission from the gas that is responding to the variable continuum. Constant or slowly varying contaminating spectral features vanish in the rms spectrum. Thus, line-width measurements can be made in both the mean spectrum and the rms spectrum: How well correlated are the line widths in the mean and rms spectrum? With what confidence can one use line-width measurements from the mean spectrum (or a single spectrum) as a proxy for the line-width measurements in the rms spectrum? In the following, we will refer to line-width measurements made in the mean spectrum with a subscript “M” (e.g., FWHM_M and σ_{M}) and measurements in the rms spectrum with a subscript “R” (e.g., FWHM_R and σ_{R}) as we attempt to address this key issue.

In a recent contribution (Dalla Bontà et al. 2020), we argue that for a variety of reasons σ_{R} is superior to FWHM_R for determination of BH masses from reverberation data. Use of FWHM_R rather than σ_{R} introduces a bias in the mass scale by stretching it—higher masses are overestimated and lower masses are underestimated. The question that we now wish to begin to address is what line width measure in the mean spectrum is the best proxy for σ_{R} ? Equivalently, when we have only a single spectrum of an AGN, what is the best way to estimate its BH mass, and how much uncertainty is introduced by using various line-width measures?

In our recent contribution (Dalla Bontà et al. 2020), we address several issues regarding estimation of BH masses from single-epoch spectra. A major conclusion of that study is that σ_{M} and FWHM_M are both suitable proxies for σ_{R} in the case of the $H\beta$ emission line, though σ_{M} is preferable. In the case of the C iv $\lambda 1549$ line, however, σ_{M} is a suitable proxy for σ_{R} , but FWHM_M is not. Among the goals for further investigation described by Dalla Bontà et al. (2020) is to consider whether other line-width measures might be suitable proxies for σ_{R} ; a lingering concern about σ_{M} is contamination of the wings of the line by other spectral features that generally do not appear in rms spectra and are therefore only an issue in dealing with mean or single-epoch spectra. In this contribution, we report on the preliminary results of our investigation.

2 | DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

As this is a preliminary report, we have considered at this point only a (sizeable) fraction of the data used by

¹A major result of the Dalla Bontà et al. (2020) study is that the luminosity of the broad $H\beta$ line is an excellent proxy for the AGN luminosity. This is especially useful if there is significant contamination of the AGN luminosity by starlight from the host galaxy.

Dalla Bontà et al. (2020). Specifically, we use the database studied by Peterson et al. (2004) and Collin et al. (2006), although we omitted three data sets where either the mean or rms spectrum was poorly defined.

The width of the $H\beta$ emission line was measured in the mean and rms spectra of 58 reverberation data sets. In addition to measurement of FWHM and σ_{line} , we considered two additional line-width measures, both of which will be less sensitive than σ_{line} to blending in the far wings.

- *Mean absolute deviation (MAD)*: This line width measure is defined by

$$\text{MAD} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |v|P(v) dv}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(v) dv}. \quad (5)$$

While σ_{line} weights the flux at velocity v as the square of the velocity displacement, MAD weights the flux linearly with v , resulting in relatively lower weight of the wings.

- *Interpercentile velocity (IPV)*: Following Whittle (1985), this measure is defined by

$$\text{IPV}(N\%) = v_2 - v_1, \quad (6)$$

where v_1 and v_2 are in turn defined by

$$\int_{-\infty}^{v_1} P(v) dv = \int_{v_2}^{\infty} P(v) dv = \left(\frac{p}{2}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(v) dv, \quad (7)$$

i.e., a fraction $p/2$ of the total line flux lies at velocities less than v_1 and the same fraction of the total line flux lies above v_2 . For example, IPV(20), i.e., $p = .2$, is the velocity range v_1 (where $v_1 < 0$) to v_2 (where $v_2 > 0$) that comprises 80% of the line flux.

Both of these measures are expected to mitigate, but not obviate, problems due to blending in the line wings.

2.1 | Characterizing line widths

Line-flux measurements were made in the simplest possible way, by defining continuum regions on either side of the $H\beta$ complex, interpolating between them, and then integrating the flux from the short-wavelength limit of the emission line to either the long-wavelength limit or just shortward of the [O III] $\lambda 4959$ narrow line, whichever is encountered first; this is illustrated in figure 1 of Peterson et al. (1991), although here we have removed the $H\beta$ narrow-line component whenever it could be accurately assessed. Measurements were done in this way because many of the best reverberation spectra cover too small

a wavelength range to do anything more sophisticated.² We note that failure to remove the narrow component of $H\beta$, depending on its strength relative to the broad component, will result in a line width that is too low, thus underestimating the black hole mass. The bias introduced can be large for FWHM and IPV (although the magnitude depends on the threshold adopted) and, except in unusual cases like NGC 4151, small for MAD and σ_{line} .

Reverberation data sets are composed of some number N individual spectra ($N \approx 30$ is typical for the data considered here). We evaluate the various line widths and their associated uncertainties through a Monte Carlo (MC) method. For each MC realization, we select N spectra at random, allowing multiple selections of individual spectra; a particular spectrum that is selected M times is weighted by M in forming the mean and rms spectra for that realization. We carry out 1,000 individual realizations for each data set and for each we measure σ_{line} , FWHM, MAD, and IPV(10), IPV(20), IPV(30), and IPV(40) in both the mean and rms spectra. We then use the 1,000 individual measurements to determine the mean and associated uncertainty for each line-width measure.

In Figure 1, we show the relationships between σ_{R} on one hand and σ_{M} , FWHM_{M} , and MAD_{M} on the other. Similarly, in Figure 2, we show the relationship between σ_{R} and IPV_{M} (10) and IPV_{M} (20) and in Figure 3, we show the relationship between σ_{R} and IPV_{M} (30) and IPV_{M} (40).

2.2 | Fitting procedure

We use the fitting algorithm described by Cappellari et al. (2013) that combines the Least Trimmed Squares technique of Rousseeuw & van Driessen (2006) and a least-squares fitting algorithm that allows errors in all variables and includes intrinsic scatter, as implemented by Dalla Bontà et al. (2018) and by Dalla Bontà et al. (2020). The fits we perform here are of the general form

$$y = a + b(x - x_0), \quad (8)$$

where x_0 is the median value of the observed parameter x . The best fit minimizes the quantity

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{[a + b(x_i - x_0) - y_i]^2}{(b\Delta x_i)^2 + (\Delta y_i)^2 + \varepsilon_y^2}. \quad (9)$$

where Δx_i and Δy_i are the errors on the variables x_i and y_i , and ε_y is the width σ of the Gaussian describing the

²We note that the primary goal of reverberation studies has been to capture, in the least model-dependent way, the emission-line variability, not necessarily the entire emission-line flux.

FIGURE 1 The relationship between $H\beta$ line dispersion in the rms spectrum σ_R and the mean σ_M spectrum (*left*), between σ_R and the mean absolute dispersion in the mean spectrum MAD_M (*middle*) and between σ_R and full-width at half maximum in the mean spectrum $FWHM_M$ (*right*). The solid lines are the fits given in Table 1. The short- and long-dashed lines represent the $\pm 1\sigma$ and $\pm 2.6\sigma$ error envelopes, respectively. The red dotted line shows where the two quantities are equal

FIGURE 2 The relationship between line-dispersion in the rms spectrum σ_R and interpercentile velocities IPV_M at the 10% (*left*) and 20% (*right*) levels. Lines are as indicated in Figure 2

distribution of intrinsic scatter in the y coordinate. The observed scatter is

$$\Delta = \left\{ \frac{1}{N-2} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i - a - b(x_i - x_0)]^2 \right\}^{1/2}. \quad (10)$$

The value of ε_y should be added in quadrature to the error in x when y is used as a proxy for x .

3 | RESULTS

The results of our fits to the data are shown in Figures 1–3 and are summarized in Table 1. The relationships between σ_R and σ_M and between σ_R and $FWHM_M$ have been previously studied (Dalla Bontà et al. 2020, their table 3). The fits given in our Table 1 are consistent with the Dalla Bontà et al. (2020) values, though the observed scatter in the

FIGURE 3 The relationship between line-dispersion in the rms spectrum σ_R and interpercentile velocities IPV_M at the 30% (left) and 40% (right) levels. Lines are as indicated in Figure 1

TABLE 1 Line-width relations

x	y	$a \pm \Delta a$	$b \pm \Delta b$	x_0	ϵ_y	Δ
$\log \sigma_M$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.222 ± 0.011	1.137 ± 0.083	3.324	0.074 ± 0.010	0.083
$\log MAD_M$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.242 ± 0.009	1.050 ± 0.066	3.245	0.065 ± 0.009	0.074
$\log FWHM_M$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.256 ± 0.013	0.569 ± 0.052	3.612	0.090 ± 0.011	0.097
$\log IPV_M(10)$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.232 ± 0.012	1.162 ± 0.098	3.869	0.085 ± 0.011	0.094
$\log IPV_M(20)$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.234 ± 0.010	1.067 ± 0.075	3.751	0.073 ± 0.010	0.082
$\log IPV_M(30)$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.235 ± 0.010	0.993 ± 0.064	3.647	0.066 ± 0.009	0.076
$\log IPV_M(40)$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\log \sigma_R$ (km s ⁻¹)	3.243 ± 0.009	0.930 ± 0.058	3.554	0.064 ± 0.009	0.073

$\sigma_R - FWHM_M$ relationship is somewhat larger ($\Delta = 0.114$) than the value found here.

Clearly, all the various line-width measures in the mean spectra are well-correlated with σ_R , which is reassuring. Notably, the slope of the relationship is close to unity in the case of MAD_M and $IPV_M(30)$, and the match of zero-points is excellent in the case of MAD_M . Interestingly, the $\sigma_R - FWHM_M$ relationship has both the largest intrinsic error and the largest deviation from a slope of unity – $FWHM_M$ is the *worst* proxy for σ_R found in this study.

4 | CONCLUSIONS

In this preliminary investigation based on a limited database comprising only the broad $H\beta$ emission line, we find that MAD_M and IPV_M both track σ_R well. This suggests that MAD and IPV can be used to estimate

BH masses from single-epoch spectra; indeed, MAD and $IPV(30)$ appear to be better for mass estimates than σ_M , and all the line-width measures we have considered seem to be superior to $FWHM_M$. Our next step will be to expand the database on include all the sources in the Dalla Bontà et al. (2020) study, to expand this study to additional emission lines, such as C iv $\lambda 1549$ and Mg ii $\lambda 2800$, and to investigate the effects of other parameters, such as line asymmetry, on these conclusions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Open Access Funding provided by Università degli Studi di Padova within the CRUI-CARE Agreement.

ORCID

Elena Dalla Bontà <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9931-8681>

Bradley M. Peterson <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6481-5397>

REFERENCES

- Batiste, M., Bentz, M. C., Raimundo, S. I., Vestergaard, M., & Onken, C. A. 2017, *ApJL*, 838, L10.
- Bentz, M. C., Peterson, B. M., Pogge, R. W., Vestergaard, M., & Onken, C. A. 2006, *ApJ*, 644, 133.
- Bentz, M. C., Peterson, B. M., Netzer, H., Pogge, R. W., & Vestergaard, M. 2009, *ApJ*, 697, 160.
- Bentz, M. C., Walsh, J. L., Barth, A. J., et al. 2010, *ApJ*, 726, 993.
- Bentz, M. C., Kenney, K. D., Grier, C. J., et al. 2013, *ApJ*, 767, 419.
- Blandford, R. D., & McKee, C. F. 1982, *ApJ*, 255, 419.
- Cappellari, M., Scott, N., Alatalo, K., et al. 2013, *MNRAS*, 432, 1709.
- Collin, S., Kawaguchi, T., Peterson, B. M., & Vestergaard, M. 2006, *A&A*, 456, 75.
- Corbett, E. A., Croom, S. M., Boyle, B. J., et al. 2003, *MNRAS*, 343, 705.
- Dalla Bontà, E., Davies, R. L., Houghton, R. C. W., D'Eugenio, F., & Méndez-Abreu, J. 2018, *MNRAS*, 474, 339.
- Dalla Bontà, E., Peterson, B. M., Bentz, M. C., et al. 2020, *ApJ*, 903, 112.
- Du, P., & Wang, J.-M. 2019, *ApJ*, 886, 42.
- Du, P., Lu, K.-X., Zhang, Z.-X., et al. 2016, *ApJ*, 825, 126.
- Du, P., Zhang, Z.-X., Wang, K., et al. 2018, *ApJ*, 856, 6.
- Fine, S., Croom, S. M., Hopkins, P. F., et al. 2008, *MNRAS*, 390, 1413.
- Fonseca Alvarez, G., Trump, J. R., Homayouni, Y., et al. 2020, *ApJ*, 899, 73.
- Grier, C. J., Martini, P., Watson, L. C., et al. 2013a, *ApJ*, 773, 90.
- Grier, C. J., Peterson, B. M., Horne, K., et al. 2013b, *ApJ*, 764, 47.
- Grier, C. J., Pancoast, A., Barth, A. J., Fausnaugh, M. M., Brewer, B. J., Treu, T., & Peterson, B. M. 2017a, *ApJ*, 849, 146.
- Grier, C. J., Trump, J. R., Shen, Y., et al. 2017b, *ApJ*, 851, 21; Erratum: 2018, *ApJ*, 868:76.
- Kaspi, S., Smith, P. S., Netzer, H., Maoz, D., Jannuzi, B. T., & Giveon, U. 2000, *ApJ*, 533, 631.
- Kaspi, S., Maoz, D., Netzer, H., Peterson, B. M., Vestergaard, M., & Jannuzi, B. T. 2005, *ApJ*, 629, 61.
- Kollatschny, W. 2003, *A&A*, 407, 461.
- Kollmeier, J. A., Onken, C. A., Kochanek, C. S., et al. 2006, *ApJ*, 648, 128.
- Martínez-Aldama, M. L., Czerny, B., Kawka, D., Karas, V., Panda, S., Zajaček, M., & Życki, P. T. 2019, *ApJ*, 883, 170.
- McLure, R. J., & Jarvis, M. J. 2002, *MNRAS*, 337, 109.
- Onken, C. A., & Peterson, B. M. 2002, *ApJ*, 572, 746.
- Onken, C. A., Ferrarese, L., Merritt, D., Peterson, B. M., Pogge, R. W., Vestergaard, M., & Wandel, A. 2004, *ApJ*, 615, 645.
- Pancoast, A., Brewer, B. J., & Treu, T. 2011, *ApJ*, 730, 139.
- Pancoast, A., Brewer, B. J., Treu, T., Park, D., Barth, A. J., Bentz, M. C., & Woo, J. H. 2014, *MNRAS*, 445, 3073.
- Peterson, B. M. 1993, *PASP*, 105, 247.
- Peterson, B. M. 2014, *Space Sci. Rev.*, 183, 253.
- Peterson, B. M., & Wandel, A. 1999, *ApJL*, 521, L95.
- Peterson, B. M., & Wandel, A. 2000, *ApJL*, 540, L13.
- Peterson, B. M., Balonek, T. J., Barker, E. S., et al. 1991, *ApJ*, 368, 119.
- Peterson, B. M., Ferrarese, L., Gilbert, K. M., et al. 2004, *ApJ*, 613, 682.
- Rousseeuw, P., & van Driessen, K. 2006, *Data Min. Knowl. Discov.*, 12, 29.
- Shen, J., Vanden Berk, D. E., Schneider, D. P., et al. 2008a, *AJ*, 135, 928.
- Shen, Y., Greene, J. E., Strauss, M. A., Richards, G. T., & Schneider, D. P. 2008b, *ApJ*, 680, 169.
- Vestergaard, M. 2002, *ApJ*, 571, 733.
- Vestergaard, M. 2004, *ApJ*, 601, 676.
- Vestergaard, M., & Peterson, B. M. 2006, *ApJ*, 641, 689.
- Vestergaard, M., Fan, X., Tremonti, C. A., Osmer, P. S., & Richards, G. T. 2008, *ApJL*, 674, L1.
- Wandel, A., Peterson, B. M., & Malkan, M. A. 1999, *ApJ*, 526, 579.
- Whittle, M. 1985, *MNRAS*, 213, 1.
- Woo, J.-H., Yoon, Y., Park, S., Park, D., & Kim, S. C. 2015, *ApJ*, 801, 38.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Elena Dalla Bontà carries out her research activities at the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Padua, Italy, and is associated with “INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova”. She is member of the International Astronomical Union. Her scientific interests include dynamics and evolution of galaxies and measurements of masses of supermassive black holes in quiescent and active galaxies.

How to cite this article: Dalla Bontà, E., & Peterson, B. M. 2022, *Astron. Nachr.*, 343, e210070.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/asna.20210070>